

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This final issue of J.UCS in the year 2001 contains two papers, which, one more time, are an excellent example of the 'universality' of the journal. I hope you'll find the papers interesting - if you have any comments or criticism, do use the unique feature of attaching your comments directly to the paper!

The year 2001 has brought a number of changes and innovations - a substantial effort was put into a new layout with a number of improved features (typed annotations, extended search options etc.). Additionally, four of the special issues published this year are also available in print and can be ordered till stocks are exhausted by sending an email to info@jucs.org. Clearly, the possibility of a concurrent electronic and printed publication increases the attractiveness of the special issues substantially.

With almost 1200 pages and 5 special issues, the year 2001 has been a good year for J.UCS and has further confirmed the importance and good standing of the journal. Naturally, this would not have been possible without the steady support of a great number of people. So let me take this opportunity to express my thanks to all those whose interest and efforts make this journal run: contributors for choosing J.UCS for the publication of their articles, all members of the editorial board who use their valuable time to review the submissions, editors of special issues for selecting J.UCS as a medium of publication, subscribers for their support of our journal, and last but not least the J.UCS editorial staff and the Know-Center (<http://www.know-center.at>) for its substantial financial support.

So - please do keep supporting J.UCS by encouraging your students and colleagues to submit papers or to do so yourselves, by helping with reviewing and endorsing subscriptions on behalf of your university or organization. Together, we'll take J.UCS into its - incredible - 8th year!

With very best wishes for 2002, from myself, the other Editors-in-Chief Cris Calude, Arto Salomaa, Klaus Tochtermann and the J.UCS team in Graz, Austria.

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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